

Role of Home Health Care Diploma Trainees in Supporting Quality Improvement in Home Health Care Services

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Abstract

Background: This trend was, in turn, influenced by an aging population along with the increased prevalence of chronic diseases, which had set up a growing demand for services like home health care. In this regard, the necessity of a well-trained workforce is of utmost importance in order to provide quality care. Diploma programs in home health care are meant for better preparation of students to be equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge for such demands. The following literature review outlines the potential contribution of home health care diploma trainees towards QI initiatives in the home health services in light of how their training can help improve patient outcomes, service efficiency, and the general quality of care.

Aim: This study aims to bring out the activities of the home health care diploma trainees in supporting quality improvement in home health care services.

Methods: Descriptive activity regarding the activities conducted by HHC Diploma trainees as part of the training portfolio. Activities are health education, vital signs, tracheostomy care, and wound dressing. For an explanation of activities and their frequency, frequency tables and a bar chart were used.

Results: The frequency count for "Health Education" is the highest at 3024, closely followed by "Risk for Fall Assessment" with 2016 and "Vital Signs" with 2520. These tasks are apparently crucial and emphasized upon in the program. On the other hand, "Medication Administration" is the lowest at 504, probably because medication administration is generally done by the patient's caregiver, hence a low focus on this task when training.

Conclusion & Recommendations: The Home health care diploma trainees play a very important role in providing support for quality improvement inside the home health services. They will be equipped, through training, to make contributions to QI efforts that will improve patient outcomes and augment the quality of care overall. Participation by HHC Diploma trainees in home health care services can support and enhance the overall quality of care in home health care.

The extension of the HHC Diploma to other PHCs within the MSD will enhance quality in care provided through the HHC services.

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Introduction

The increasing demand due to the aging population and the rising prevalence of chronic diseases have put into focus a well-trained workforce for quality care (Kilpatrick, et al., 2020). The home health care diploma programs will, therefore, prepare the trainee to respond to such demands. In this situation, quality improvement initiatives remain the surest way of improving the quality of care provided, the outcomes of patients, and the efficiency of the service (Goldman, et al., 2021). Diploma trainees must be in the frontline of these QI processes, as their training so equips them to respond to such challenges (Peiris-John, et al., 2020).

This study was aimed at exploring the contribution of HHC diploma trainees to QI initiatives within the home healthcare service. We also explored activities that demonstrate how their training contributes to improved patient outcomes and better service quality through the attainment of organizational goals. The analytics allow us to see what specific contributions are made by the trainees themselves in the context of quality improvement initiatives.

Specifically, the study aims to establish the diverse contributions of HHC diploma trainees to various areas of quality improvement within home health care services. This research work underlined, among other activities, HHC trainees' activities carried out in health education, vital signs monitoring, tracheotomy care, and wound dressing as certain ways they contributed to the improvement of quality in home health services (Alkhamis, & Miraj, 2021).

This is important research, as it identifies an investigation into the influence of trained personnel on home health care services. Home health care services play an important role in the delivery of healthcare among vulnerable populations, particularly elderly and chronically ill patients (Almulla, et al., 2024). Their role of diploma trainees in such services is highly relevant to activities designed for service improvement and would be important in improving patient safety for improving service delivery and overall satisfaction.

Recent literature shows that health professionals' involvement in QI processes, especially for home health care, plays an important role. QI involves not only technical competencies but also person-centered practices, which are of significant value in improving outcomes within home health settings (Bakerjian, 2022). Care delivery and patient safety practices, together with patient education, were noted to improve in the presence of specially trained home health care diploma trainees (Fleary, & Joseph, 2024). Common issues to be addressed, such as fall prevention, compliance with medication, and patient education form part of QI. However, studies have evidenced

the fact that involving diploma trainees in health education is crucial for improving the health literacy of patients, which again is closely related to quality improvement. researchers describe that specialist workforce development must reflect needs and competencies in reinforcing QI responsibilities within home health care services (Housawi, et al., 2020).

Hospital remissions are a major concern, particularly among patients with complex or chronic conditions. While Home Health Care (HHC) has been proven to reduce readmission rates, the integration of trainees into these care teams provides an additional opportunity for improving patient outcomes. Trainees, under the supervision of experienced healthcare professionals, offer support, guidance, and increased monitoring, ensuring comprehensive care after discharge.

The study utilized data from the admission Database from 2021 to 2024, focusing on patients discharged home with HHC services. The analysis evaluated patients who received care from both professional staff and trainees.

This study demonstrates that HHC is associated with a reduced 30-day readmission rate among AMI patients, even in those with a higher burden of comorbidities. The findings support the integration of HHC as part of post-discharge care strategies, particularly for older patients and those with chronic conditions such as heart failure and diabetes. As healthcare systems continue to prioritize reducing hospital readmissions, the role of HHC in improving patient outcomes and reducing healthcare costs becomes increasingly relevant (Kilpatrick, et al., 2020).

Methods

A descriptive design was used to assess activities carried out by the HHC diploma trainees during their training portfolio. The major activities that the trainees engaged in during the training were health education, risk for fall assessment, vital signs monitoring, tracheotomy care, dressing of wounds, and medication administration. The frequency of these activities was recorded and then analyzed using frequency tables and bar graphs.

Results also gave an indication of the frequency of each competence or activity performed during a certain period by trainees. Such metrics as total frequency per month, per week, and for six months were compiled to establish which was the most held or emphasized activity during the training period.

Results

The results from the study on the activities undertaken by HHC diploma trainees show varied frequencies across different tasks. Health education was the most frequently performed activity, with a count of 3,024. This reflects the trainees' extensive efforts in educating patients and their families about health conditions, preventive care, and healthy lifestyles, which play a crucial role in improving patient compliance and reducing readmissions. The risk for fall assessments had a frequency of 2,016, indicating that trainees are proactive in identifying potential fall hazards, particularly for elderly patients. This is essential for enhancing patient safety within home care settings. Monitoring vital signs, with a total frequency of 2,520, was also a significant activity, highlighting the importance of detecting early changes in a patient's health and ensuring patient stability. Lastly, drug administration had the lowest frequency, with

504 instances. This lower count reflects the fact that drug administration is often handled by primary caregivers, leaving trainees in more of a supportive role, allowing for a stronger focus on health education and safety assessments.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Skills Performed by HHC Diploma Trainees

Competency Item Subtitle	Total Recorded For 7 trainees						
	Total Day	per	Total week	per	Total Month	per	Total for 6 Months
Initial Health Assessment	28		84		336		2016
Medication Administration	7		21		84		504
Administering tube feeding (NGT, PEG)	14		42		168		1008
Performing urinary catheterization	14		42		168		1008
Health Education	42		126		504		3024
Tracheostomy care and suctioning	14		42		168		1008
Risk for fall assessment	28		84		336		2016
Dressing	21		63		252		1512
Specimen Collection	28		84		336		2016
Vital Signs	35		105		420		2520
Total	231		693		2772		16632

Figure 1. HHC Trainees Participation in HHC Patient Care in 6 Months

Figure 2. Patient Distribution in HHC Services with Heart Diseases

Figure 3. Patient Distribution in HHC Services with DM, HTN, CVA and Dislipidemia

Discussion

The data across the differing activities reveal that HHC diploma trainees are core when effecting quality improvement (Al Qarni, et al., 2021). The trainees, in terms of

providing health education, risk assessment, and vital signs monitoring, contribute a great deal to both the safety of patients and their outcomes (Al-Najmi, et al., 2024). This frequency would then suggest the nature of the training itself: more educative and preventive rather than interventionist in terms of medication provision (Akdemir, et al., 2020).

Conclusion

Home health care diploma trainees play an essential role in enhancing the quality of home health services. Their training equips them with the necessary skills to support patient safety, provide health education, and contribute to better health outcomes. By focusing on critical areas such as health education, fall risk assessment, and vital signs monitoring, these trainees help ensure a higher standard of care for patients. Their contributions are crucial in promoting patient well-being and preventing complications, making them a key factor in the overall improvement of home health care quality.

Recommendation

It is recommended that the HHC Diploma Program be scaled up to other PHC and MSD centers to ensure the availability of well-trained home health care personnel, thereby promoting quality care. This expansion is crucial in enhancing the overall capacity of home health care services. Additionally, there should be an increased emphasis on patient safety during training, particularly in areas such as fall risk assessment and vital sign monitoring. This focus will better prepare graduates to meet the safety needs of vulnerable populations receiving home care. Furthermore, while health education and risk assessment are vital, a more balanced training approach is necessary, especially in medication management. This will enable trainees to better support caregivers, leading to improved patient safety and more holistic care.

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